

KEY ASPECTS IN MANUFACTURING MULTI-SCALE COMPOSITES USING OOA RFI

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ABSTRACT

This paper documents the manufacturing of multi-scale polymer-matrix composites (PMCs) featuring carbon nanotubes (CNTs) in the resin, using the out-of-autoclave (OOA) resin film infusion (RFI) process. Quality of the multi-scale PMCs was assessed primarily in terms of porosity, fibre volume fraction (V_f), CNT distribution and inter-laminar shear strength (ILSS). Five experimental programs were undertaken. Flat PMC panels with thicknesses around 4 mm featuring symmetric, balanced and orthogonal lay-ups were fabricated under different processing conditions, and characterized. Various bagging configurations were used. The programs aimed at developing knowledge and directives on how to produce high quality multi-scale OOA RFI PMCs.

1 INTRODUCTION

The aerospace industry is steadily increasing its use of polymer-matrix composites (PMCs) in airframe structures as it seeks to benefit from the high specific in-plane strength of the materials. However, PMC laminates suffer from low inter-laminar shear strength due to their weaker polymer-matrix. In the case of brittle thermosetting polymer matrices e.g. epoxy, cracks can propagate rapidly between reinforcement layers resulting in catastrophic failure. Hence, minimising the risk of delamination is of paramount importance for improving the safety of PMC structures.

Several solutions exist for toughening PMCs and lowering the crack propagation rate, including the modification of polymer matrices through toughening agents [1, 2]. Nano-reinforcements with high aspect ratios such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs) were identified as promising toughening agents. However, improvements in mechanical properties resulting from the addition of CNTs differ widely, even for constant loadings of the same CNTs, based on processing conditions and CNT distribution in the matrix [3]. For example, Geng et al. [4] observed a 60% improvement in impact fracture toughness from adding only 0.25 wt% of multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) to a neat epoxy. Another advantage of CNTs is that unlike polymer-based toughening agents [5] they do not affect adversely the glass transition temperature of polymer matrices, and they can even lead to increases in the glass transition temperature [1, 3, 4].

Unfortunately, the use of polymer resins loaded with nano-reinforcements for the fabrication of PMCs remains limited due to difficulties in processing. The increase in resin viscosity caused by the addition of nano-reinforcements leads to poorer processability compared with neat resins [1, 6]. Also, it is challenging to obtain PMCs featuring nano-modified resins with a uniform distribution of nano-reinforcement, resulting in potentially weaker regions of neat resin. This can be attributed to a marked tendency of nano-reinforcements towards agglomeration when they are given sufficient mobility [7], but also to filtering caused by the dense fibre network of fabric reinforcements [6].

A robust solution for manufacturing multi-scale PMCs effectively at an industrial scale is still lacking, where the effects of viscosity increase and nano-reinforcement filtration are mitigated by minimising resin flow distances. The processing technique should favour through-thickness resin flow as opposed to in-plane flow. Moreover, nano-reinforcements such as CNTs tend to align in the resin flow direction when subjected to sufficient levels of shear stress [8]. Such alignment is particularly useful in improving the weak inter-laminar properties of PMCs as nano-modified polymers are stronger when their nano-reinforcements are aligned in the loading direction [9]. Thus, the selected

manufacturing technique should lead to multi-scale PMCs that are reinforced by continuous in-plane fibre reinforcements and through-thickness nano-reinforcements.

OOA RFI was identified [1, 2] as a potential process for manufacturing multiscale PMCs with nano-modified resins. Resin films and fabric layers can be stacked with various possible levels of interleaving. Using RFI, the initial distribution of nano-reinforcements in the resin film can be controlled, and short resin flow lengths in the through-thickness direction can limit filtering and orient the nano-reinforcements. However, no exhaustive analysis of RFI for manufacturing multi-scale PMCs was reported, aside from limited data collected from tensile, compressive and inter-laminar fracture toughness testing [1, 2]. This paper documents the effect of processing parameters including fabric architecture, resin formulation, CNT loading, bagging method and level of interleaving on the quality of PMCs in terms of void content, fibre volume fraction and inter-laminar strength. Five distinct experimental programs were completed as reported below.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Resin films

Five hot-melt pre-catalysed B-stage epoxy-based resin films were used in this work, Table 1. The first four films F1, F2, F3 and F4 differed in resin formulation and CNT loading. These four resin films were made from two resin formulations R1 and R2 which featured different viscosities and glass transition temperatures of 160°C and 180°C after cure. Films of both formulations were also loaded with 0.3 wt% multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs). The fifth epoxy-based resin film F5, SA70 from Gurit, was used for assessing the effect of resin formulation. The film consists of a neat prepreg resin with lower flowability than the above four infusion resins. The F5 resin film featured a light glass fibre support carrier which remained in PMC parts following RFI processing.

Film	Resin	CNTs (wt%)	Surf. dens. (g/m ²)	T _g (°C)	Visc. 60°C (Pa·s)	Film thick. (µm)	Void cont. (wt%)	Gel time (min)	Surf. tens. (mJ/m ²)	Contact angle (°)
F1	R1	0	222	160	190	190	0.38	136	42.0	22.9
F2	R1	0.3	255	160	260	217	0.43	135	42.1	22.7
F3	R2	0	228	180	61	191	0.44	106	42.5	23.1
F4	R2	0.3	228	n/a	n/a	221	0.40	104	41.9	22.0
F5	SA70	0	150*	120	n/a	n/a	n/a	46	34.6	25.9

* SA 70 features a 25 g/m² glass fibre carrier

Table 1: Resin film properties

2.2 Reinforcement fabrics

Five HTS40 PAN carbon fibre fabrics were used for manufacturing multiscale PMC laminates, including twills 2×2 and non-crimp stitched fabrics, Table 2. Codes identify the architecture followed by letter L for low surface density, H for high surface density and P for powder binder. The fabrics enabled comparisons for the cover factor, surface density and architecture.

Fabric	Style	Orient.	Surf. dens. (g/m ²)	Yarn count	Yarn width (mm)	Yarn spac. (mm)	Transverse permeability (10-13 m ²)
Twill-L	Twill 2x2	(0/90)	205.2	3K	1.70	1.99	5.3 ± 0.2
Twill-H	Twill 2x2	(0/90)	403.2	6K	1.89	2.01	26.8 ± 1.6
NCF-L	NCF tricot-warp	(-45/+45)	254.1	12K	1.70	1.81	2.6 ± 0.2
NCF-H	NCF chain stitch	(-45/+45)	537.8	12K	1.60	1.76	10.8 ± 1.0
NCF-HP	NCF chain stitch*	(-45/+45)	535.0	12K	n/a	n/a	n/a

* with powder binder

Table 2: Reinforcement fabric properties

2.3 Manufacturing process, stacking and bagging

The RFI stacking process consists in laying fabric and resin film plies in a specific sequence. Bulk and interleaved stacking configurations were tested, Figure 1. The number of resin films was selected towards targeting a conservative V_f value of 55% in consolidated laminates, with an extra 10% added for bleeding and limiting risks of resin starvation.

In bulk RFI, separate stacks of fabrics and films were prepared and superimposed, resulting in no interleaving. Fabric reinforcement stacks were balanced square symmetric. Resin films were stacked together using a laminating roller, forming a thick single layer of resin. Finally, the dry fabric stack was laid over the resin film stack. In interleaved RFI, stacks were made by layering fabric plies and resin films alternatively, leading to full interleaving. The fabric plies and resin films were compacted together using a laminating roller. Fabric reinforcement lay-ups were balanced square symmetric.

Figure 1: Bulk (left) and interleaved (right) RFI stacking configurations

Bagging methods B1 to B2 and I1 to I4 were used for bulk and interleaved stacks respectively, Table 3, Figure 2. Consolidation proceeded under 0.98 bar vacuum pulled until complete cure. Ancillaries included a 6 mm flat aluminium tool and caul plate, bag, release film, perforated release film (0.14% open area), breather, sealant tape and dam, glass weave and release agent. Method B1 was the baseline approach for bulk stacks. Stack edges were sealed with a dam, ensuring through-thickness resin flow. Two layers of breather were placed over the entire assembly. Method B2 featured edge breathing instead of surface breathing used in method B1. Method I1 was the baseline approach for interleaved stacks. Edge breathing was used for extracting air and volatiles out of the stack. Method I2 used a metal frame around the edges of the stack and a caul plate on its surface for controlling resin bleed. Breathing was ensured through a bleeder ply positioned between the caul plate and stack. Method I3 differed from I1 only by the absence of the non-perforated release film covering both the stack and dam. Method I4 was similar to I1 but it did not feature a caul plate.

Bagging method	Bleeding	Caul plate	Sacrificial breather ply	Surface release film
B1	Surface	Yes	Yes	
B2	Edge	Yes	No	
I1	Edge	Yes		Yes
I2	Surface	Yes		No
I3	Edge	Yes		No
I4	Edge	No		Yes

Table 3: Bagging methods

3 VISCOUS AND CAPILLARY FORCES

3.1 Description

Experimental program M-VC featured 4 laminates manufactured to evaluate the effect of viscous and capillary forces on RFI PMC manufacturing, Table 4. Laminates were made using resin films F3 and F5 with the lowest and highest ratios of viscosity to surface tension respectively. Laminates M-VC-01 and M-VC-02 were resin starved while laminates M-VC-03 and M-VC-04 were resin rich, featuring 50% more resin than required for a fibre volume fraction V_f of 0.55.

Figure 2: Bagging methods a) B1, b) B2, c) I1, d) I2, e) I3, f) I4

Program	Laminate	Fabric	Resin	% CNT loading	Stacking	Bagging
M-VC	M-VC-01	NCF-HP	SA70	0	Interleaved	I2
	M-VC-02	NCF-HP	R2	0	Interleaved	I3
	M-VC-03	NCF-HP	SA70	0	Interleaved	I2
	M-VC-04	NCF-HP	R2	0	Interleaved	I3
M-BL	M-BL-01	NCF-H	R2	0	Interleaved	I4
	M-BL-02	NCF-H	R2	0	Interleaved	I3
	M-BL-03	NCF-H	R2	0	Interleaved	I1
	M-BL-04	NCF-H	R2	0	Interleaved	I5

Table 4: Description of flat PMC laminates for programmes M-VC and M-SC

3.2 Results

Starved laminate M-VC-01 was made using film F5. Cross-sections showed that resin filled inter-yarn gaps before filling yarns as indicated by dry regions at the center of yarns, Figure 3a. It follows that for film F5, flow was governed by the permeability of the reinforcement, with viscous forces dominating over capillary forces.

Starved laminate M-VC-02 was made using film F3. Cross-sections showed that resin was wicked by the yarns, leaving inter-yarn gaps free of resin, Figure 3b. This typical case of over-bleeding suggests capillary forces overtaking viscous forces. Care must be applied in preventing excessive bleeding when fabricating laminates.

Resin rich laminate M-VC-03 made using film F5 featured a smooth resin rich surface on the bottom tool side. Resin rich zones were distributed along yarns and they were more frequent in the

Figure 3: Laminate cross-sections a) M-VC-01, b) M-VC-02

center of the laminate. Conversely, the top surface contacting the bleeder ply featured a rough surface with a uniform resin distribution. Laminate thickness was $5.28 \text{ mm} \pm 0.10 \text{ mm}$, with a thicker region in the center of the laminate due to reduced bleeding.

Laminate cross-sections revealed resin rich zones between fabric plies caused in part by the glass carrier in resin film F5. Closer inspection of laminate cross-sections using optical microscopy revealed that inter-yarn gaps were well saturated with resin, with some yarns featuring internal micro-voids, Figure 4a. Resin flow was influenced strongly by low yarn permeability, indicative of viscous forces dominating over capillary forces.

Unlike laminate M-VC-03, the fabrication of laminate M-VC-04 resulted in a significant amount of resin flow into the breather material, clogging the vacuum port and confirming that film F3 used here flowed much more readily than film F5. Inspection of M-VC-04 showed a thickness of $4.10 \text{ mm} \pm 0.05 \text{ mm}$ with greater resin flow leading to more uniform thickness than for M-VC-03. Despite a clear excess of resin, both surfaces of the laminate featured pinholes aligned with the inter-yarn gaps.

The cross-section of laminate M-VC-04 featured many macro-voids located in inter-yarn gaps, Figure 4b, highly reminiscent of those observed in starved laminate M-VC-02. This suggests that despite the resin rich nature of this RFI stack, excessive wicking occurred nonetheless. Hence, film F3 resin required rigorous control of bleeding, which was not achieved using bagging method I3.

Figure 4: Laminate cross-sections a) M-VC-03, b) M-VC-04

3.3 Findings

The four laminates in experimental program M-VC showed that resins behave very differently in RFI, depending on their properties. Resin flows predominantly inside or around yarns depending of the relative strengths of viscous and capillary forces, resulting in different void formation mechanisms. Flow of film F5 was largely governed by the permeability of the fabric leading to micro-voids within yarns, whereas flow of film F3 was mostly governed by capillary forces leaving macro-voids in inter-yarn gaps. Thus, upon designing an RFI manufacturing process it is crucially important to select a resin formulation that can limit void formation, as well as a suitable bleeding method for controlling breathing and bleeding.

4 BLEEDING CONFIGURATION

4.1 Description

Experimental program M-BL was devised for evaluating the effectiveness of various bleeding configurations in mitigating excessive wicking observed in experimental program M-VC. Four

laminates were fabricated using distinct bleeding configurations. Edge bleeding was used in all cases to minimize resin loss; details appear in Table 4. For comparison purposes, all laminates featured the same materials and were manufactured concurrently inside the same vacuum bag.

4.2 Results

Traces of resin were observed in the breather plies after cure. Inspection revealed that the amount of resin bleed varied depending on bleeding configuration. M-BL-02 showed the most resin bleed of all laminates. This was caused by the gap between the caul plate and edge dam that enabled resin to flow directly into the breather plies, bypassing the glass fabric bleeder ply of the resin dam. It is worth noting that M-BL-02 used the same bleeding method used in experimental programme M-VC, which also featured strong bleeding. M-BL-03 showed the second-most abundant resin bleed, slightly more abundant than M-BL-01 but much less than M-BL-02. M-BL-04 showed the least amount of resin bleed. This was expected due to the smaller resin escape path, resulting from the glass fabric bleeder covering only 5% of the total perimeter of the laminate.

Removal of the vacuum bag revealed that all faces of the laminates in direct contact with the tool or a caul plate featured smooth surfaces. Only the face of laminate M-BL-01 in contact with the breather ply featured a rough surface.

Measurements of laminate thicknesses along the length of the laminates showed that all laminates except M-BL-01 had a relatively uniform thickness. For M-BL-01, the lack of a caul plate prevented uniform compaction which resulted in resin accumulating at the centre of the laminate, a region less subjected to edge bleeding. The use of a caul plate also increased resin bleed significantly as seen by much lower thicknesses for laminates M-BL-02, M-BL-03 and M-BL-04 compared with laminate M-BL-01.

Fibre volume fraction V_f values appear in Figure 5a. The trends relate to those observed for thickness, where the absence of a caul plate results in much lower V_f . In addition, the reduction of bleed in laminate M-BL-04 also led to a lower fibre volume fraction compared with the other laminates featuring a caul plate.

Porosity values for the laminates appear in Figure 5b. The highest level of porosity was obtained in laminate M-BL-02 which featured the highest amount of bleed. However, laminate M-BL-04 showed that an excessive restriction on bleed can also lead to high porosity. In this case, porosity was not caused by excessive wicking but by insufficient breathing of the stack, which limited extraction of gasses such as air and volatiles. Laminates M-BL-01 and M-BL-03 featured low levels of porosity as they achieved a good balance between restricting bleed and enabling gas extraction. It is worth noting that bagging methods used for making these two laminates differ only in the use of a caul plate. Hence, the use of a caul plate is not the dominant factor for controlling porosity.

Figure 5: M-BL laminates a) fibre volume fraction, b) porosity

4.3 Findings

Experimental programme M-BL showed that the bleeding configuration has a strong influence on the consolidation of laminates. Results showed that the use of a caul plate enhances the surface finish of laminates, and it improves thickness uniformity by increasing bleeding. More importantly, the bleeding configuration has a direct effect on laminate porosity. Limited restriction of bleeding can result in excessive wicking of resins subjected to strong capillary forces, while excessive restriction of

bleeding can prevent the effective extraction of gases within laminates. In this work, bagging method I1 was found to be the best bleeding configuration.

5 STACKING CONFIGURATION

5.1 Description

Experimental program M-SC studied differences in laminates caused by the level of interleaving of resin films within stacks. Full interleaving (interleaved RFI) and no interleaving (bulk RFI) stacking methods were compared. The objective was to identify any potential differences in fabricated laminates due to varying levels of resin film interleaving in the stacking sequence.

Five laminates were fabricated using films F1 to F4 featuring the highest and lowest viscosities, Table 5. Laminates M-SC-01 through M-SC-04 were made with highly similar bagging methods I1 and B2 using edge bleeding in order to minimise the number of variables affecting processing. Conversely, laminate M-SC-05 featured a bagging method designed specifically for the through-thickness flow of bulk RFI.

Program	Laminate	Fabric	Resin	% CNT loading	Stacking	Bagging
M-SC	M-SC-01	NCF-H	R2	0	Bulk	B2
	M-SC-02	NCF-H	R1	0.3	Interleaved	B2
	M-SC-03	NCF-H	R2	0	Interleaved	I1
	M-SC-04	NCF-H	R1	0.3	Bulk	I1
	M-SC-05	NCF-H	R2	0	Bulk	B1
M-PC	M-PC-01	NCF-H	R2	0	Interleaved	I1
	M-PC-02	NCF-H	R2	0	Interleaved	I1

Table 5: Description of flat PMC laminates for programmes M-SC and M-PC

5.2 Results

For laminates featuring edge bleeding (M-SC-01 to M-SC-04), the interleaved RFI laminates featured smooth surfaces with occasional pinholes. The same was observed for bulk RFI laminate M-SC-02 that was made with the higher viscosity resin. However, the use of a lower viscosity resin in laminate M-SC-01 resulted in a laminate that featured a large non-saturated region on its face that was in contact with the caul plate.

The non-saturated region was caused by the resin flowing in the through-thickness direction faster at the edges than at the centre of the stack due to a difference in local permeability arising from the glass fabric used for edge bleeding. This closed the air evacuation channels at the edges of the stack before sufficient saturation could be achieved, entrapping a large quantity of air under the caul plate. As mentioned above, this behaviour was not observed with the nano-modified film F2 and was attributed to a more uniform resin flow front which minimised air entrapment.

Bagging method B1 was designed specifically for preventing non-saturated regions in bulk RFI. Instead of relying on edge bleeding, the bagging method seals the edges of the stack with sealant tape and bleeding is achieved through a bleeder ply at the surface of the stack. This method is highly effective in preventing non-saturated regions from occurring at the surface of the stack, but the absence of direct contact between the laminate and caul plate results in a rough laminate surface.

All laminates were analysed for fibre volume fraction and porosity in saturated regions; results appear in Table 6. In the case of fibre volume fraction V_f , no clear trends were found. Edge bleeding had no effect on the fibre volume fraction compared with surface bleeding, while the level of resin film interleaving affected the fibre volume fraction within yarns slightly. However, laminates differed greatly in terms of porosity. Results showed that the use of a higher viscosity resin filled with CNTs decreased the void content significantly compared with a low viscosity resin.

The level of interleaving also had a strong effect on the porosity of laminates fabricated with edge bleeding, whereas bulk RFI led to an important reduction in porosity compared with interleaved RFI. However, edge bleeding cannot be used reliably with bulk RFI due to risks of air entrapment.

Unfortunately, the use of surface bleeding in laminate M-SC-05 resulted in an increase in porosity that negated most of the benefits associated with bulk RFI.

Laminate	Resin film	Level of interleaving	Bagging method	Volume fraction (%)			Porosity (%)
				V_{fy}	V_y	V_f	
M-SC-01	F3	None	B2	64.6	90.1	58.2	1.8
M-SC-02	F2	None	B2	65.2	87.0	56.7	0.1
M-SC-03	F3	Full	I1	66.3	86.0	57.0	2.8
M-SC-04	F2	Full	I1	71.6	85.7	61.4	1.2
M-SC-05	F3	None	B1	64.2	90.3	58.0	2.5

Table 6: Fibre volume fractions and porosity for experimental programme M-SC

5.3 Findings

Experimental programme M-SC showed that the level of interleaving of resin films within stacks has a strong effect on the quality of laminates. Results showed that in certain cases, the absence of resin film interleaving in bulk RFI reduces porosity in laminates compared to the full interleaving of interleaved RFI. However, it was shown that bulk RFI requires surface bleeding for limiting risks of air entrapment, leading to surface roughness.

6 PRE-COMPACTION

6.1 Description

De-bulking is an important step in manufacturing PMC parts from pre-preg; external pressure and vacuum are applied to a stack before cure, aiming at removing air entrapped between pre-preg plies and at minimising void formation during consolidation. Experimental program M-PC investigated the benefits that vacuum-assisted pre-compaction of stacks, or de-bulking, may bring to RFI.

In theory, de-bulking should have minimal impact in RFI as the dry fabric reinforcements provide air evacuation channels for reducing air entrapment. Moreover, pre-compaction does not assist significantly the distribution of resin within inter-yarn gaps of tight fabrics.

Two laminates were fabricated for experimental programme M-PC, Table 5. Stack M-PC-01 did not undergo any pre-compaction prior to cure, whereas stack M-PC-02 was compacted between platens thrice, to 1 MPa, at a rate of 1 mm/min using an Instron 4482 load frame. Vacuum was applied during the entire duration of compaction, contributing to air removal.

6.2 Results

Both laminates featured smooth surfaces. Laminates M-PC-01 and M-PC-02 had similar thicknesses of $4.11 \text{ mm} \pm 0.04 \text{ mm}$ and $4.13 \text{ mm} \pm 0.02 \text{ mm}$ respectively. The analysis of cross-sections revealed that pre-compaction still resulted in voids in inter-yarn gaps. Moreover, pre-compaction did not affect the fibre volume fraction. Pre-compaction to 1 MPa may reduce porosity slightly, by 0.3% in this case, but this may also be attributed to variability. Hence, pre-compaction does not appear to be worthwhile for RFI manufacturing.

6.3 Findings

Results suggest that despite the use of large compaction pressures of 1 MPa, pre-compaction is not useful for improving the quality of RFI parts. The procedure does not provide an increase in fibre volume fraction nor does it reduce porosity considerably.

7 FABRIC, RESIN FORMULATIONS AND CNTS

7.1 Description

Experimental program M-FR was a multivariate series of experiments aimed at identifying the effect the fabric architecture, fabric surface density, resin formulation and CNT loading on V_f , porosity

and ILSS of laminates. A 2-level, full factorial design of experiments was performed, leading to the manufacturing of 16 laminates, Table 7. The full factorial design, Table 8, enabled the investigation of all main effects of factors, and of all interactions of 2, 3 and 4 factors.

Factor	Level	
	Low	High
A: Fabric architecture	Twill	NCF
B: Fabric surface density (g/m ²)	<260	>400
C: Resin formulation	1	2
D: CNT loading (wt%)	0	0.3

Table 7: Full factorial design for experimental programme M-FR

Program	Laminate	Fabric	Resin film	% CNT loading	Stacking	Bagging
M-FR	M-FR-01	NCF-H	F2	0.3	Interleaved	I1
	M-FR-02	NCF-H	F1	0	Interleaved	I1
	M-FR-03	NCF-L	F2	0.3	Interleaved	I1
	M-FR-04	NCF-L	F1	0	Interleaved	I1
	M-FR-05	Twill-H	F2	0.3	Interleaved	I1
	M-FR-06	Twill-L	F2	0.3	Interleaved	I1
	M-FR-07	Twill-H	F1	0	Interleaved	I1
	M-FR-08	Twill-L	F1	0	Interleaved	I1
	M-FR-09	NCF-H	F3	0	Interleaved	I1
	M-FR-10	NCF-L	F3	0	Interleaved	I1
	M-FR-11	Twill-L	F3	0	Interleaved	I1
	M-FR-12	Twill-H	F3	0	Interleaved	I1
	M-FR-13	NCF-H	F4	0.3	Interleaved	I1
	M-FR-14	Twill-H	F4	0.3	Interleaved	I1
	M-FR-15	Twill-L	F4	0.3	Interleaved	I1
	M-FR-16	NCF-L	F4	0.3	Interleaved	I1

Table 8: Description of flat PMC laminates for programme M-FR

7.2 Results

All laminates featured flat surfaces due to the combination of the interleaving RFI method and the use of a caul plate, but the amount of surface defects varied between them. For example, laminates featuring CNTs had smoother surfaces while those featuring NCF fabrics had more pin holes.

Differences between laminates also affected the V_f , porosity and ILSS, Table 9. The total V_f was relatively constant between laminates, in the mid-50s. Conversely, porosity and ILSS varied significantly. Laminate M-FR-06 had the lowest porosity at 0.1%, and highest ILSS at 78.8 MPa. These values were obtained with a low surface density twill and resin film R2. On the other hand, laminate M-FR-09 had the highest porosity at 2.8% and lowest ILSS at 45.0 MPa. These values were obtained with a high surface density NCF and resin film R3.

Results showed a fairly strong correlation between the ILSS of laminates and porosity, As expected, laminates featuring more voids tended to have weaker inter-laminar strength. However, ILSS was affected by more than porosity alone, and it is difficult to identify the role of each of the 4 factors and their interactions from raw data. Hence, the data set obtained from the experiments was analysed more thoroughly using statistical tools, namely by examining the effect of each contrast on each response. The effects of contrasts on the fibre volume fraction inside yarns, V_{fy} , appear in Figure 6a. Several contrasts had comparable contributions to V_{fy} , including main factors and interactions between factors. This suggests that the variability that was observed is likely inherent to OOA RFI and not to the investigated factors, i.e. selection of materials. However, limited variation in V_{fy} was observed, less than $\pm 2\%$.

Laminate	Volume fraction (%)			Porosity (%)	ILSS (MPa)
	V_{fy}	V_y	V_f		
M-FR-01	63.5	87.4	55.5	0.9	55.4
M-FR-02	66.4	86.6	57.5	1.5	53.5
M-FR-03	62.9	88.6	55.7	1.3	75.0
M-FR-04	64.2	89.9	57.7	1.8	67.8
M-FR-05	68.6	83.8	57.5	0.5	63.4
M-FR-06	65.0	85.6	55.6	0.1	78.8
M-FR-07	64.3	83.6	53.8	2.4	59.9
M-FR-08	62.4	85.8	53.5	0.7	72.7
M-FR-09	66.3	86.0	57.0	2.8	45.0
M-FR-10	62.1	86.0	53.4	2.2	61.3
M-FR-11	66.6	87.7	58.4	1.8	67.8
M-FR-12	66.0	83.9	55.4	1.7	54.8
M-FR-13	63.6	83.7	53.3	2.3	49.9
M-FR-14	61.5	82.0	50.4	2.0	58.1
M-FR-15	65.9	86.1	56.8	1.2	74.6
M-FR-16	61.4	84.8	52.1	1.8	70.7

Table 9: Fibre volume fractions and porosity for experimental programme M-SC

The effects of contrasts on the yarn fraction V_y appear in Figure 6b. Results showed that factors A and B were the greatest contributors to V_y . The use NCFs increased V_y by 1.8% compared with twills, and higher surface density fabrics reduced V_y by 2.2%. These differences are directly related to the geometry of fabrics. For example, crimped yarns in weaves reduce the packing of yarns compared with NCFs. Additionally, in the case of weaves, thinner yarns result in more straight fibres and better packing. However, similarly to V_{fy} the difference in V_y between laminates is small.

The effects of contrasts on the global fibre volume fraction of laminates V_f appear in Figure 7a. Considering that V_f was calculated from V_{fy} it is expected that there would be little correlation with any of the main factors. The strongest variations resulted from contrasts representing the interactions of multiple factors, suggesting that differences are likely caused by the out-of-autoclave RFI process and not by material selection. This is interesting, considering that the type of fabric had a fairly strong influence on the compaction of stacks. Hence, the presence the resin plays a significant role in the reorganization of the fibre networks in fabrics during RFI processing.

The effects of contrasts on the porosity V_v of laminates appear in Figure 7b. Results showed that the main factors are the strongest contributor to porosity levels. The greatest source of porosity was the use of resin formulation R2 instead of R1. Potentially, this may be caused by the lower viscosity of formulation R2 which can increase the likelihood of over-bleeding. The CNT loading, fabric architecture and surface density all had similar contributions to porosity. The addition of CNTs reduced porosity, and this behaviour appears to be attributable to the increase in viscosity. NCFs increased porosity compared to twills while higher surface density fabrics increased porosity.

The effects of contrasts on the ILSS of laminates appear in Figure 8. Results showed that ILSS was predominantly affected by the main factors. Most importantly, the use of low surface density fabrics brought a clear benefit to ILSS. This can be linked in part to the lower porosity resulting from such fabrics, but it is not the sole factor given the extent of the improvement. Advantages of thin-ply laminates relate to delayed micro-cracking of the matrix. Weaves improved the ILSS compared with NCFs; this may be due to the higher delamination resistance of woven laminates compared with UD laminates. Resin formulation R1 improved ILSS; this is likely attributable to lower porosity levels. Finally, the addition of CNTs improved the ILSS slightly.

7.3 Findings

Multivariate experimental programme M-FR quantified the effect of fabrics, resin formulation and CNT loading on fibre volume fraction, porosity and ILSS of laminates. Results showed that material selection played a major role over porosity and ILSS but less on fibre volume fraction.

Figure 6: Programme M-FR: effect of contrasts on a) fibre volume fraction V_{fy} in yarns, b) yarn fraction V_y

Figure 7: Programme M-FR: effect of contrasts on a) global fibre volume fraction V_f , b) porosity V_v

Figure 8: Programme M-FR: effect of contrasts on ILSS

Additionally, porosity was found to be a relatively good metric for the ILSS of laminates. The best combination of materials for low porosity PMCs was a low surface density fabric with a resin having a viscosity that is not too low to prevent over-bleeding. Regarding multi-scale PMCs, results showed that on average the addition of 0.3 wt% of CNTs improved the ILSS by 8.5%.

8 CONCLUSION

The fabrication and characterisation of flat laminates revealed that PMCs of very different quality can be obtained using out-of-autoclave RFI, depending on processing conditions. It was shown that porosity is a good metric for the inter-laminar resistance of PMCs and that it is affected by the level of resin film interleaving in stacks, bagging method, and by the selection of resin film and fabric.

More specifically, porosity was related to resin viscosity, fabric surface density, CNT loading, level of breathing and bleeding, and the direction of resin flow. Guidelines for making high quality PMC parts can be proposed from these results. For example, PMC parts with low porosity should be made with a relatively high viscosity resin, a low surface density fabric and use of CNTs. This study of flat laminates enabled the identification of key issues in RFI processing. More detail can be found in [10].

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